
Research

Suppliers Network Optimization Model for fruit dealers in Namibia Context (Concept of multiple trip and split delivery with time constraints)

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Abstract: This paper attempts to discuss Supply Chain Network Optimization in the context of multiple and split delivery vehicle routing problems. There is a likelihood of efficient supply chains to minimize costs as well as improve reliance on what would be called shared networks (demands and agents). Ancient optimization models have limitations in adopting the concept of a multi-depot and split delivery. As such, this writeup elaborates more on the supply chain network optimization model: Multi-Split delivery vehicle routing problem, commonly abbreviated MDSDVRP. This model factors in different constraints in the objective function i.e. multi depot, split delivery, and timed constraints. The resultant function minimizes the supply chain's delivery times, operations, and several vehicles and, increases customer satisfaction.

Keywords: Multi split delivery, MDSDVRP, MTVRP, Network Optimization, Supply chain

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Introduction

The concept of VRP was first coined by (Dantzig & Ramser, 1959). Over time, it has found relevance in logistics where customer's requirements get fulfilled. In the VRP, a problem with a single depot, it would imply that shipping times would be increased. As such, the service would be unsatisfactory in the case of many customers. A lot of companies are trying hard to achieve an efficient supplier network. However, the secret lies in the optimization of those supplier networks. Most of the companies lack the knowledge of systems aimed at understanding the complexity and analysis of data purposed to provide end-to-end view. Therefore, supply chain network optimization refers to all the processes geared to achieving a whole view of any entity's supply chain. They comprise model preparation, and the establishment of appropriate formulae that replicates the entire set of business transactions needed to initiate a complete

transformation. The model serves to assess the various parameters and constraints for optimizing supplies besides limiting the costs.

A vehicle routing problem is one of the optimization methods. Owing to the growing complexity of real-life practical systems, various modifications have been done to the Vehicle Routing Problem. One of the practical problems is the supply chain of Perishable food (fruits) in Namibia. The fact that they are perishable implies that they have a short shelf life. Hence, there is a need to cut the delivery time to get the fruits to the market while fresh. Companies are known to have unique logistic plans. The logistics cover the areas of routes, customers, depots, the fleet of vehicles, locations, etc.

Literature review

According to (Wilk and Cavalier 2016), a VRP with a single limitation is called a capacitated vehicle routing problem. From one depot location, different fleet routes would be established to limit traversed lengths. The split delivery vehicle routing problem let the demand of the consumers to be fulfilled by several visits (Yan et al., 2017). An improved model of this problem is handled by the creation of a heuristic algorithm. Whenever time windows are considered in a network model problem, then it is referred to as a vehicle routing problem with windows (Yan et al., 2017). The time consideration slackens the model such that each customer has a specific window frame to be served. As such, it becomes fundamental to schedule a fleet of vehicles (Sharda, 2018).

Ray et al., (2015), acknowledge systems that enable many depots to be allowed to serve clients. However, when the focus shifts to locating those distribution depots and elaborating on all likable routes to serve the potential clients then it becomes a multi-depot split delivery. Each company's logistics department handles emergent issues differently. Logistical issues are multi-leveled: strategic, tactical as well as operational. Each of the levels is issue-based. For instance, the strategic level attempts to seek solutions to issues through the careful location of the multi-depots in strategic places to serve potential clients. As such, the network is partitioned before the application of resource allocation algorithms subject to prevailing inputs. Upon completion, operational analysis comes in, to plan for possible routes using different algorithms. The tactical approach serves to implement the routing activities based on the previous considerations. The underlying principle is to reduce logistic costs.

The motivation behind the model remains to meet large-scale demands such as fulfilling the smooth flow of humanitarian deliveries and facilitating disaster relief i.e. rescue missions and crises. There are withstanding gaps that require optimal sharing responsibilities. As such, the need for sufficient optimization systems has been required to boost commodity delivery. Theoretical findings and numerical experiments with solution methods demonstrate that splitting deliveries is feasible and can result in significant travel distance savings (Archetti and Speranza, 2012). Dror and Trudeau (1989, 1990) introduced the split delivery vehicle routing problem (SDVRP), which has since been thoroughly examined by, Archetti, Savelsbergh, and Speranza (2008) and Archetti, Bianchessi, and Speranza (2011).

Metaheuristic techniques are used to tackle the split delivery vehicle routing problem (SDVRP) the most. These include local search (Dror and Trudeau, 1989, 1990), tabu search (TS, Archetti, Speranza, and Hertz, 2006, Berbotto, García, and Nogales, 2014, Qiu, Fu, Eglise, and Tang, 2018), genetic algorithm (GA, Wilck and Cavalier, 2012), hybrid metaheuristics (Rajappa, Wilck, and Bell, 2016) and particle swarm optimization (Shi, Zhang, Wang, and Fang, 2018). The use of aggregated/disaggregated mathematical formulations, such as benders decomposition, valid inequalities, tailored optimization techniques based on branch-and-cut frameworks, and a new and tailored branch-and-cut algorithm for the split delivery vehicle routing problem with time windows (SDVRPTW), has recently produced high-quality results (Bianchessi and Irnich, 2019).

Dragon Fruit Farmstead Features Fruit Supply Context

With peasants who make farm house choices based on forward buy-in deals with dealers, the dragon fruit source chain flinches. Dealers sell fruits to distributors who, in turn, distribute, export, and by-product producers assign the fruit and by-products. The dragon fruit supply chain is shown in Figure 1. Characteristic of dragon fruit by-products are violet and packed dried fruit appetizers. Dragon fruit is characteristically planted twice a year in Namibia. Harvesting starts one year after the farmstead, but the fruit is at the excellence required for marketable resolves 2–10 years after harvest.

Figure 1. The dragon fruit supply chain

Dragon fruit crop typically depends on age and a tree is usually only measured prolific until the age of 12 years. Figure 2, shows the typical crop curve as a meaning of tree age.

Figure 2. Characteristic of dragon fruit crop as a purpose of tree age

Procedure

In this paper, the technique is related to the ranked planning approach that divides the decision-making process into strategic and operational stages. Decisions are first taken at the strategic level of secret preparation and then at the working level. Figure 3, updated by Ahumada et al., demonstrates how realistic the graded approach can be for the dragon fruit chain.

A practical demonstrative strategy for decision-making for dragon fruit farming and harvesting in Namibia can be obtained in this paper. As stated earlier, this strategy looks at setting up and wounding (which are tactical choices) over a multi-year planning horizon. The possible downside of ranked planning is that farmers may be engaged in increasing revenues and output outcomes. In other words, it is beneficial for several parties to coordinate strategic and working decisions: farmers, manufacturers, retailers, and sellers.

Figure 3. Example of a ranked scheduling schematic

Figure 3, presents a visual representation of the management planning process, which consists of two distinct phases. In the initial phase, decisions pertaining to crop selection, truncation, and the timing and quantity of planting are made exclusively at the beginning of the season. These crucial determinations set the foundation for the subsequent steps in the planning process.

This paper introduces a deterministic optimization model developed specifically for the advancement of dragon fruit cultivation in Namibia, focusing on the hierarchical planning diagram. While the primary objective of this study revolves around the secondhand dragon fruit market, it is important to note that the proposed model holds potential for application in other fresh fruit production chains as well. The versatility and adaptability of the model make it a valuable tool for optimizing decision-making processes in various agricultural contexts.

Underlying Assumptions

The Vehicle Routing Problem is assumed to be classical. That is to imply that every customer has a definite demand for a specific commodity. However, there is a finite fleet of vehicles each having a maximum capacity. The vehicle used for delivering fresh fruits is capacitated to leave and return to a depot. While on the route, it is not restricted at all for as long as it is within that length. For every location, there is a single vehicle not exceeding the capacity. All vehicles are homogeneous in capacity. Multi-split assumes that several depots have equal capacities to meet location demands. Each depot has the same number of vehicles with each of them having a definite capacity. In the split delivery problem, each

client's demands are met by one or more fleets. To formulate the problem, we assume that no preexisting depot has been established. The location of the clients serves as the basis for determining the depot location. Each depot is responsible for meeting the demands of its assigned clients. The objective is to optimize the delivery process by dividing the clients' demands among the available fleets.

Objectives

- Evaluating the optimal count of depots as well as their locations without pre-established depot locations
- Finding the optimal cost incurred to serve all client's demands
- Finding the optimal fleet of vehicles to complete the shared activities
- Determining shared routes per vehicle with minimal cost

Table 1. Notation

Sign	Explanation
N	Customer count
P	Vehicle count
q_i	Demand for each customer, i
r_{ij}	consumption per route in i and j nodes
d_{ij}	Length nodes i, j
$X_{i,j,k}$	Edge i, j served by Fleet k
y_{ik}	demand i by fleet k
Q	Fleet's capacity
Q_c	Demand per customer in every fleet
Q_r	Consumption of a route per fleet
t	Time
W	Depot

From the above, we have N clients represented as a node. Also, we have M count of the fleet with Linear Programming Optimization Model.

Assumptions and hypotheses

For this model:

1. Objects (farms) are already functioning because the models do not deal with system decisions.
2. The time for strategic planning is 10 years flat and takes into account two harvest seasons (rainy and dry seasons) for each year.
3. Fruit trees are expurgated when they are 10 years old or older if the model chooses (for example, if the future prices of other harvests are higher than the planted crop). Decisions are made to cut or replant only in the first season.
4. The delivery of income, demand, and market prices is characterized by their predictable values.

5. It is not allowable to store fresh dragon fruit. However, the fruits can be used for by-products such as dry snacks and mauve.
6. Amounts for reaping and planting of each crop are decision variables that do not exceed the prearranged extreme land area.
7. The choice variables of the model are the new planting and cutting areas of each planting area and the quantity of fruits sent to clientele (traders, wholesalers, and by-product producers) each year.
8. Other results cover the amount of fruits to be sold to customers and the amount of labor (fixed and part-time) required covering all actions in the model.

Objective Function

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Max } O = & \sum_j \sum_i \sum_s \sum_t p_{jist} \cdot ST_{jist} + \sum_j \sum_m \sum_s \sum_t q_{jmst} \cdot SWM_{jmst} \\
 & + \sum_j \sum_s \sum_t r_{jst} \cdot SB_{jst} - \sum_j \sum_t cp_{jt} \cdot Y_{jt} - \sum_j ch_t \cdot X_{jkt-1} \\
 & - \sum_j crt \cdot Z_{1j,k=10,t} - \sum_t Ft \cdot cLabf - \sum_t Hiret \cdot cLabp - \sum_j cbp_{st} \cdot SB_{jst} - \sum_t \sum_s \sum_j cPNT_{jist \cdot ijst} \\
 & - \sum_{Ks} \sum cwaterks \cdot wks - \sum_j \sum clightings \cdot vjs
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The legitimacy of the estimation method is to assess decisions on planting and harvesting that take advantage of the farmers' expected benefits. This is the variance net revenue from sales to traders (ST), inter-board markets (SWM), and suppliers of by-products (SB) and the costs of the planting, shortening, and other incentives for the crop. Missing missions, labor, cost of lighting, fines for hydration.

The first category of constraints (2, 3, and 4) relates to the availability of resources such as land, water, and lighting, and whether the farmer has access to these resources. These constraints can impact the feasibility of planting and harvesting decisions and must be considered when assessing the expected benefits of these decisions.

$$\sum_J \sum_k X_{jkt} \leq L \quad \forall t$$

Total of the area of each crop at age *cannot* surpass the available land (L).

- Water limit

$$\sum_J \sum_k X_{jkst} \cdot w_{jkst} \leq W_{st} \quad \forall t, s$$

At all ages of trees k the required amount of water per hectare for each crop j differs in the seasons of the year t ; it cannot exceed the presence of water. Also, the yield decreases if the trees are watered too much.

- Lighting restrictions

$$\sum X_{js} \cdot v_s \leq V_s \quad \forall s$$

Since there is no sunlight in the dry season, bright lighting methods should be used at night. One hectare of light is required for each fruit of the plant each year which is varied but limited. Restrictions (5) and (6) apply to the location of the farm and the crop.

$$\sum X_{jtk} \geq U_{jt} \quad \forall t$$

Limitations (5), small restrictions on the cultivation area of each crop at a time, which may lead to new contracts. The plan defines the minimum planting area for each crop according to the user agreement. The U parameter can be 0, but it must be less than the region availability.

- Harvest

$$\sum_j ST_{jst} + \sum_k SWM_{jkst} + SB_{jst} \leq \sum_m \gamma_{jkst} X_{jkst} \quad \forall j, s, t$$

Constraint (6) ensures that the total yield is less than the yield (metric tons per hectare) multiplied by the area of the farm (hectares).

The constraints in the third category (7-15) are related to the planning structure of agricultural models, particularly those related to farm age balance and the cutting and replanting of new species. For example, in the case study of apple and pear trees in Catale [10], the simulation of cutting and replanting was used to assess the impact of these practices on farm age balance and overall productivity. These constraints are important to consider when developing agricultural models and planning for the long-term sustainability of the farm.

$$X_{j, k, s = 1, t} = X_{j, k, s = 2, t} \quad \forall j, k, t$$

Constraints (7) ensure that the area sown of each crop does not change throughout the year. (That is, between the first and second seasons). This is because the decision of planting or pruning is only made at the beginning of the first season. Agricultural decisions were made by Y_{jt} . The age of newly planted fruit trees is always 0. There are two types of pruning: $Z1_{jkt}$, optional for $k = 1 \dots 9$, and $Z2_{j, k = 10, t}$, mandatory for all 10-year-old trees.

$$X_{jkst} = Y_{jt} \quad \forall j, k = 1, t = 1$$

Constraint (8) states that only new plants can be planted in the first year (age group 1).

$$X_{jkst} = I_{j, k-1} - Z1_{jkt} \quad \forall j, k = [2 \dots 9], t = 1$$

Constraint (9) is similar to constraint 8 and occurs only in year 1 but for other age groups.

(K = 2..9):

Agricultural land is considered to be the number of trees in the age group k-1 in year 0, less than, can be cut after one year or during the first year.

$$X_{jkt} = I_{j,k-1} - Z_{2jkt} \quad \forall j, k = 10, t = 1 \quad (10)$$

The Constitution states that when determining the pre-sowing area, it is necessary to reduce the annual yield from 10 years.

$$\sum X_{jkt} = \sum Y_{j,t-1} - \sum Z_{1jkt} \quad \forall j, k = 1, t > 1$$

The Constitution (11) states that in the planning horizon, the planting area for the period t > 1, for the age group k = 1 is determined by the new crop sown annually before the removal of the cut from the new farm the following year.

$$X_{jkt} = X_{j,k-1,s,t-1} - Z_{1jkt} \quad \forall j, 10 > k > 1, t > 1$$

Restriction (12) is intended for crop aging in the age group 10 > k >. The size of the farm for special years depends on the previous year. If desired, cut smaller areas.

$$Z_{2jkt} = X_{j,k-1,s,t-1} \quad \forall j, k = 10, t > 1$$

The Constitution (13) states that all 9-year-old t-1 plants must be pruned the following year.

- Restrictions on work

$$F_t + Hire_t - P_t \cdot \sum_j Y_{jt} - H_t \cdot \sum_j X_{jt} - R_t \cdot \sum_j Z_{jkt} = 0 \quad \forall t$$

Model of work requirements limitation (14) for planting, cutting, and harvesting in a given year.

$$F_t = M \quad \forall t$$

The number of employees is sometimes fixed. If this is the case, this amount should be given to full-time staff.

$$Hire_t \leq N \quad \forall t$$

Several part-time employees based on plantation, harvest, or felling needs are needed. However, the number is limited due to estimates, which can be seen from the limitations (16). The last sets of constraints (17) - (19) are designed to meet demand.

$$\sum_j ST_{jist} = d_{jist} - j_{ist} \quad \forall t, s$$

The restriction (17) is a soft restriction at the request of the trader because downstream flow is allowed.

$$\sum_j SWM_{jmst} = e_{jmst} \quad \forall t, s$$

Constraint (18) states that the demand of wholesalers should be satisfied.

$$\sum SB_{jt} = f_t \forall t$$

The Constitution (19) says that the demand for by-products must be met.

Min Z=

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \sum_{j=0}^k \sum_{p=1}^P b_{ij} X_{ij}^p \tag{2}$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^k Y_i^p \leq Q_i, \quad p = 1, 2, 3, \dots, P \tag{3}$$

$$\sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{i=1}^k X_{ij}^p \geq 1, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, k \tag{4}$$

$$\sum_{p=1}^P Y_i^p = I_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k \tag{5}$$

$$A_i \leq \text{Max } t_i \leq B_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k \tag{6}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^k X_{ih}^p = \sum_{j=1}^k X_{hj}^p \quad h = 1, 2, \dots, k; p = 1, 2, \dots, P \tag{7}$$

$$Y_i^p = h_{i1}^p I_i^1 + h_{i2}^p I_i^2 + \dots + h_{im}^p I_i^m, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k; p = 1, 2, \dots, P \tag{8}$$

$$f = \min V_i - \sum_{m=1}^M v_i^m, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k \tag{9}$$

$$0 \leq x_i^m \leq W - w_i^m, x_i^m + (1 - \text{right}_{mn})M \geq x_i^n + w_i^n \tag{10}$$

$$0 \leq y_i^m \leq H - h_i^m, y_i^m + (1 - \text{top}_{mn})M \geq y_i^n + h_i^n \tag{11}$$

$$0 \leq z_i^m \leq L - l_i^m, z_i^m + (1 - \text{front}_{mn})M \geq z_i^n + l_i^n \tag{12}$$

$$\text{front}_{mn} + \text{right}_{mn} + \text{top}_{mn} + \text{front}_{nm} + \text{right}_{nm} + \text{top}_{nm} = 1 \tag{13}$$

Explanations of formulas are as shown below:

1. Minimization objective function of the fleet in how it is used, P
2. Itemized objective function for the fleet traversed length
3. The limit of the fleet's capacity
4. 4 & 5 depict the location points or the serving of each customer ≥ 1 with their demands satisfied
6. The fleet access to the customer on time, between Earliest Arrival (EA) & Latest arrival time (LA)
7. Law of the conservation formula. Comparison of fleet departure v arrival
8. The requirements for splitting for each customer, while maintaining the order
9. Fleet's constraints per load
10. From 10 all through to 12 indicates cargo loads
13. The consistency of the position of loading

Solving the model using computer software

The formulated model was solved both analytically as well as with the help of a sophisticated computer heuristics algorithm. The solution serves to assess the entire Namibian Fruit dealer's transport network as well as the nodal demands. As such, it develops a kind of map that is sorted. The sorting is done by aligning costs to the respective transversal maps. The software was set as a model with 16 nodes and a combined capacity (90). The graphs below denotes the traversal network and attached demands.

The refined costs, incorporating split delivery, revealed an optimal cost of 2373. This achievement showcases the effectiveness of the solution in optimizing the transportation process for the fruit dealers.

Figure 4. Sorted map

Figure 5. Time per instance

Figure 6. Transversal plotting

Figure 7. Comparison of the inputs on the model based on average time ratio of all

Conclusion

In this research paper, we investigated the combined optimization problem of Vehicle Routing Problem with Simultaneous Pickup and Delivery (VRPSPD) with cargo loading, which is a crucial issue in the field of transportation logistics. Our aim was to find an optimal solution for this problem by developing a heuristic algorithm and a mathematical model, which is concise, efficient, and easy to implement.

Our research showed that the proposed genetic algorithm is a more feasible and effective method for solving VRPSPD with cargo loading compared to the existing methods. The algorithm we developed based on the improved genetic algorithm outperformed the traditional genetic algorithm, providing solutions that meet the actual demand for low transportation costs and low travelling costs.

Finally, we applied our algorithm to a real-world case study, and the results obtained were satisfactory. Our research has contributed to the development of a unified model for the optimization of vehicle routing and cargo loading problems. It is hoped that our research will inspire further work in this field and help practitioners to optimize their transport logistics and reduce costs.

Recommendation

Firstly, the MDSDVRP can be formulated as an optimization problem that seeks to minimize the total distance traveled by all vehicles while satisfying the demand of each customer within a given time window. The problem involves determining the optimal number of depots, the optimal allocation of customers to depots, and the optimal routing of vehicles to deliver the orders.

To solve the problem, the use of metaheuristic algorithms such as genetic algorithms, simulated annealing, and tabu search has been proposed in previous literature. These methods have been shown to provide efficient solutions in reasonable computation times for large-scale instances of the MDSDVRP.

In the case of fruit dealers in Namibia, the research paper suggests that the dealers face challenges in delivering their products due to limited transportation infrastructure, and the perishable nature of their products. Therefore, it is essential to develop an efficient delivery system that takes these factors into account.

One potential solution is to establish a network of distribution centers strategically located throughout the regions. These centers could serve as depots for the fruit dealers, providing them with a central location to store and distribute their products. The allocation of customers to depots could be determined based on the geographical location of the customers and the capacity of the depots.

Furthermore, the use of real-time monitoring systems and data analytics could be implemented to optimize the routing of vehicles and minimize the total distance traveled. This would involve collecting data on the location and demand of customers, the condition of the roads, and the availability of vehicles. This data could then be analyzed to determine the most efficient routes for each vehicle, taking into account factors such as traffic congestion, road conditions, and customer demand.

To conclude, the MDSDVRP presents a significant challenge for fruit dealers in Namibia. However, by implementing a strategic distribution network, utilizing metaheuristic algorithms, and employing real-time monitoring and data analytics, it is possible to optimize the delivery process and improve the efficiency of the system.

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